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1 **Spores potentially dispersed to longer distances are more tolerant to**
2 **ultraviolet radiation: a case study in the moss genus *Orthotrichum*¹**

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11

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18 **PREMISE OF THE STUDY:** UV radiation influences the viability of algal spores and
19 seed-plant pollen depending on the species, the dose and the wavelength. In bryophytes,
20 one of the dominant groups of plants in many habitats, UV radiation could determine
21 their spore dispersal strategy, and such data are critical for reconstructing the ancestral
22 state in plants and for determining the distribution range and perpetuation of bryophyte
23 species.

24 **METHODS:** Spores of four bryophyte species of the moss genus *Orthotrichum*, that
25 were either hygrochastic or xerochastic (spores dispersed under wet or dry conditions,
26 respectively), were exposed to realistic doses of UV radiation under laboratory
27 conditions. Spore viability was evaluated through germination experiments and, for the
28 first time in bryophytes, ultrastructural observations. Given that the UV-B doses used
29 were relatively higher than the UV-A doses, the UV effect was more probably due to
30 UV-B than UV-A wavelengths.

31 **KEY RESULTS:** All four species reduced their spore germination capacity in a UV
32 dose-dependent manner, concomitantly increasing spore ultrastructural damage
33 (cytoplasmic and plastid alterations). Most spores eventually died when exposed to the
34 highest UV dose. Interestingly, spores of hygrochastic species were much more UV-
35 sensitive than those of xerochastic species.

36 **CONCLUSIONS:** UV tolerance determines moss spore viability, as indicated by
37 germination capacity and ultrastructural damage, and differs between spores of species
38 with different dispersal strategies. Specifically, the higher UV tolerance of xerochastic
39 spores may enable them to be dispersed to longer distances than hygrochastic spores,
40 thus extending more efficiently the distribution range of the corresponding species.

41

42 **KEY WORDS** dose-response sigmoid curves; IC50; lamellar bodies; long-distance
43 dispersal; modelling; Orthotrichaceae; plastoglobuli; spore dispersal strategy; UV
44 tolerance; vacuolization.

45

46 Diaspores with an aerial dispersal stage, including most plant spores and pollen, can be
47 exposed to several harmful environmental factors, such as drought, frost and high levels
48 of ultraviolet (UV) radiation (Van Zanten and Gradstein (1988). UV radiation represents
49 nowadays only about 8% of the total solar radiation reaching the biosphere, and it is
50 divided in three wavelength intervals: UV-C (100-280 nm), UV-B (280-315 nm) and
51 UV-A (315-400 nm). UV-C is lethal for life but is absent at ground level because it is
52 absorbed by the stratospheric oxygen and ozone. UV-B is specifically absorbed by
53 stratospheric ozone, but a certain amount reaches the biosphere, having increased during
54 the last decades due to ozone degradation and other factors associated to climate change
55 (Bais et al., 2015). UV-B has traditionally been considered as a harmful environmental
56 factor for photosynthetic organisms, but nowadays it is rather contemplated as a general
57 regulator mostly inducing acclimation responses (Jansen and Bornman, 2012). Much
58 research has been conducted on the effects of UV-B radiation on the biochemistry,
59 physiology, morphology and anatomy of photosynthetic organisms, including
60 bryophytes (Suchar and Robberecht, 2016). UV-B radiation can also alter reproductive
61 processes and, specifically, algal spores and pollen of seed plants have been
62 demonstrated to be the most UV-B-sensitive reproductive stage (Roleda et al., 2006a;
63 Llorens et al., 2015). Thus, UV-B can importantly affect the viability of pollen and
64 spores during their transport, particularly when they are dispersed to long distances
65 (Bohrerova et al., 2009).

66 UV-A is the major component of UV solar radiation (around 95%), but its effects
67 on plants have been less investigated than those of UV-B, probably because UV-A is
68 less harmful and it is not related to the ecological problem of ozone depletion. UV-A
69 effects may be different to those induced by UV-B, reflecting diverse UV-perception
70 mechanisms (Verdaguer et al., 2017). As occurs with UV-B, responses of plants to UV-

71 A depend on the species, the dose and the experimental approach applied, and include
72 both inhibitory and stimulatory effects on diverse aspects of growth, development and
73 photoprotection. Specifically, the viability of pollen and spores seems to be less affected
74 by UV-A than by UV-B wavelengths in a range of seed plants and algae (Wiencke et al.,
75 2000, 2004; Tala et al., 2007; Steinhoff et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2010).

76 Spores are one of the dispersal methods used by bryophytes, thus contributing to
77 species perpetuation, especially in monoicous species. However, the effects of UV
78 radiation (both UV-B and UV-A) on spore viability and dispersal of bryophytes,
79 particularly mosses, are almost completely unknown. Only Wolf et al. (2010) conducted
80 experiments using mosses, demonstrating dose-dependent UV-B effects on spore
81 germination in the model moss *Physcomitrella patens* under laboratory conditions. Also
82 in bryophytes, but using liverworts and not mosses, Van Zanten and Gradstein (1988)
83 exposed spores to very high levels of solar radiation (including UV) at jet stream
84 altitudes, mostly showing lethal effects that were also assessed by germination tests.
85 Direct observations on the ultrastructural damage resulting from UV radiation also
86 provide an interesting, complementary method to assess spore viability. Nevertheless,
87 no data are available for bryophyte spores, although elevated UV-B radiation has been
88 demonstrated to affect the plastid ultrastructure in moss shoots (Hui et al., 2013), as
89 well as in spores of algae and pollen of seed plants (Santos et al., 1998; Koti et al.,
90 2004; Steinhoff et al., 2008).

91 To increase spore dispersal efficiency, most moss sporangia develop diverse
92 structures for the gradual release of spores, especially peristome teeth and differential
93 thickenings of the capsule wall, both responding to changes in air humidity
94 (Vanderpoorten and Goffinet, 2009). Regarding this environmental factor, the most
95 common strategy of spore dispersal in mosses in temperate regions is xerochastic (Pais,

96 1967), where the peristome allows the opening of the capsule mouth under dry
97 conditions. In contrast, other species use the hygrochastic strategy, where the capsule
98 mouth opens under wet conditions. Xerochasy is thought to favour long-distance
99 dispersal, whereas hygrochasy could be related to a safe-site strategy, favouring the
100 short-range dispersal of the spores into appropriate sites close to the parental plant, and
101 ensuring enough humidity for germination and establishment (Medina and Estébanez,
102 2014).

103 Given that moss spores are mainly transported by the wind (Goffinet et al.,
104 2009), they can be dispersed at various distances from the source, from local to
105 intercontinental scales (Vanderpoorten and Goffinet, 2009), depending on the dispersal
106 strategy of the species and the spore viability and (maybe) size. Long-distance dispersal
107 may increase the geographical range of certain species, provided that spores remain
108 viable during transportation, being able to tolerate harsh environmental conditions, such
109 as extreme temperatures, desiccation, and high radiation levels. In this sense, widely
110 distributed species produce spores that are more resistant than those of species with
111 constrained distributions (Van Zanten, 1976; Van Zanten and Gradstein, 1988).

112 The aims of our study were to test the influence of UV radiation on the spore
113 viability of mosses and, for the first time in bryophytes, to relate the UV tolerance of
114 spores with the xerochastic or hygrochastic dispersal strategies. We compared four
115 species of the speciose and cosmopolitan genus *Orthotrichum*, which includes both
116 xerochastic and hygrochastic species (Medina and Estébanez, 2014). Given that spores
117 of xerochastic species are prone to be dispersed to longer distances, thus being exposed
118 to higher UV doses, the hypothesis under study was that they would be more UV
119 tolerant than spores of hygrochastic species. To check the spore viability in response to
120 UV, we used two methodologically complementary characteristics, germination rate and

121 ultrastructure, that represent different aspects of UV effects, allowing a more integrated
122 evaluation of the damage produced in the species studied.

123

124

125 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

126

127 **Plant material**—Mature capsules of four *Orthotrichum* species (*O. acuminatum*
128 H. Philib., *O. ibericum* F. Lara and Mazimpaka, *O. rupestre* Schleich. ex Schwägr. and
129 *O. striatum* Hedw.) were collected in June-August 2012 in the following respective
130 localities: Manzanares El Real (Madrid, Spain, 40°45'51"N 3°54'18"W, 1140 m),
131 Berzocana (Cáceres, Spain, 39°24'28"N 5°25'36"W, 780 m), and Serranillos (Ávila,
132 Spain, 40°20'20"N, 4°54'23"W, 1230 m, for both *O. rupestre* and *O. striatum*). All the
133 samples were growing epiphytically on *Quercus pyrenaica* Willd. *Orthotrichum*
134 *acuminatum* and *O. ibericum* are hygrocastic, whereas *O. rupestre* and *O. striatum* are
135 xerochastic (Medina and Estébanez, 2014). Voucher specimens of the studied species
136 were deposited in the herbarium MAUAM (Universidad Autónoma de Madrid).
137 Voucher data are as follows: *O. acuminatum*, N.G. Medina & V. Mazimpaka 522
138 (MAUAM); *O. ibericum*, B. Estébanez 4085 (MAUAM); *O. rupestre*, B. Estébanez
139 4080 (MAUAM); and *O. striatum*, B. Estébanez 4081 (MAUAM).

140

141 **Irradiation experiments**—Capsules were surface-sterilized with 0.1% sodium
142 dichloroisocyanurate (10 min) and washed in sterile distilled water. Spores were
143 suspended in sterile distilled water and sown in 35 mm Petri dishes (100 µl per dish),
144 with half-strength Murashige-Skoog basal medium solidified with 1% Gelrite®. Spores
145 were cultured in a growth chamber at 24±1°C, where they were exposed for 3, 6 and 12
146 h to two different radiation regimes: photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) alone, or
147 PAR + UV radiation. Samples under the PAR regime received radiation from True-Lite
148 Industrial F40T12/TL full spectrum fluorescent tubes (True Sun, Steubenville, Ohio,

149 USA) and were covered by Ultraphan 395 (DigeFra GmbH, Munich, Germany) filters,
150 which cut off all UV radiation. Samples under the PAR + UV regime received radiation
151 from both True-Lite and Philips TL 40W/12 (Philips Lighting, Eindhoven, The
152 Netherlands) lamps, and were covered by Ultraphan 295 filters, which cut off UV-C
153 radiation (Fig. 1). The filters were pre-irradiated for 24 h and the stability of their
154 absorption properties was checked at the beginning and end of the experiment. Before
155 use, filters were sterilized with UV-C (15 min in a laminar flow cabinet). The lamps
156 were preburned for 100 h until they had reached a stable output. PAR lamps gave a
157 continuous photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD) of around $31 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ to the
158 spores (measured with a LI-190SA quantum sensor, LI-COR, Lincoln, Nebraska, USA),
159 while UV lamps gave an irradiance of 2.26 W m^{-2} of UV-B and 2.60 W m^{-2} of UV-A
160 (measured with a Macam SR9910 spectroradiometer, Macam Photometrics Ltd,
161 Livingstone, Scotland). For each exposure period, the unweighted UV-B and UV-A
162 doses to which spores were exposed were determined, and the biologically effective
163 doses were calculated using different action spectra to facilitate comparisons with other
164 studies (Table 1). Biologically effective UV-B (UV-B_{BE}) doses were calculated using
165 both the generalized plant damage action spectrum normalized to 300 nm (Caldwell,
166 1971) and the DNA damage spectrum (Setlow, 1974), and biologically effective UV
167 (UV_{BE}) doses were obtained using the more modern biological spectral weighting
168 function by Flint and Caldwell (2003), which takes into account both UV-B and UV-A
169 wavelengths. Given that this last action spectrum seems to be more realistic than
170 classical spectra (Flint and Caldwell, 2003), it was used to perform calculations and to
171 present results. Three UV levels (low, intermediate and high) were applied, according to
172 the different exposure periods (3, 6 and 12 h). The high UV-B and UV-A exposures used
173 in the experiment were approximately equivalent to respective ambient UV-B and UV-A

174 exposures of 3 and 0.1 d in summer at the altitude and latitude in which samples were
175 collected (Häder et al., 2007). Thus, the main effect of UV radiation in our experiment
176 was more probably due to UV-B than UV-A wavelengths.

177 Four replicates were established for each species, radiation regime and UV_{BE}
178 dose (including dose 0). Three replicates were used for measuring spore germination,
179 and the fourth one for ultrastructure observation. Petri dishes were randomly distributed
180 under the lamps and moved periodically to prevent the possible place-dependent
181 differences in the irradiance received by the spores.

182

183 ***Spore germination and ultrastructure***—After the irradiation experiment,
184 germination rates were recorded after 18 d of culture in a growth chamber under similar
185 levels of PFD and temperature. 100 spores or sporelings per replicate were counted and
186 recorded as germinated (living) or non-germinated (dead). Aborted spores (with no
187 cytoplasm, usually much smaller) were discarded.

188 Spore ultrastructure was observed in the samples of PAR regime (control) and
189 PAR + UV regime after the irradiation experiment, and also in uncultured spores, which
190 were taken directly from mature capsules of each species and rehydrated overnight.
191 Spores were kept in a growth chamber for a maximum of 4 d before fixation. As spores
192 of these species take at least 10 d to re-activate and germinate, only mature spores prior
193 to germination were observed. Each sample was fixed 1 h in 3% glutaraldehyde in Na-
194 cacodylate buffer (0.1 M, pH 7.2), postfixed 2 h in 1% osmium tetroxide, dehydrated in
195 an ethanol series, transferred to propylene oxide at 4°C, and slowly embedded in Spur's
196 resin in seven steps, one per day, keeping samples at 4°C without stirring (Ligrone and
197 Duckett, 1994). Ultrathin sections were made using a Leica Ultracut-S ultramicrotome
198 (Leica Mikrosysteme GmbH, Vienna, Austria), contrasted with uranyl acetate and lead

199 citrate, and observed using a JEOL-JEM 1010 transmission electron microscope (TEM,
200 JEOL Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) operating at 100 kV. Ultrastructural observations were
201 grouped into three categories of damage (non-damaged, moderately damaged, and
202 lethally damaged spores).

203

204 ***Statistical analysis***—We fit the germination data (Table 2) to dose-response
205 sigmoid curves (Fig. 2), using the UV_{BE} doses derived from the action spectrum by Flint
206 and Caldwell (2013). Given that sigmoid curves can take several forms, we applied a
207 selection protocol in order to find the curve type that best fit our data (Ritz and Streibig,
208 2015). We first fit logistic curves with three (Eqn 1) and four parameters (Eqn 2) and
209 then used Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) to select the most appropriate model (a
210 detailed description of the selection procedure is shown in Appendix S1, see
211 Supplemental Data with this article):

212

$$(Eqn1) \ g = B_t + \frac{Tp - B_t}{1 + 10^{(d-IC50)}}$$

213

$$(Eqn2) \ g = B_t + \frac{Tp - B_t}{1 + 10^{(d-IC50)*Hill}}$$

214

215 where g is the percentage of germinated spores; d is the UV_{BE} dose received; $IC50$ is the
216 dose that produced a response halfway between the maximum and the minimum,
217 indicating the effectiveness of UV_{BE} radiation to inhibit germination; B_t is interpreted as
218 the minimum asymptotic germination percentage; Tp is the maximum germination
219 percentage in spores that had not received UV treatment; and $Hill$ refers to the
220 symmetry of the curve (Table 3). As negative numbers have no biological meaning in
221 this case, B_t was constrained to positive in all models. To test the interspecific

222 differences in the main parameters of the curves (T_p , B_t and IC_{50}), we performed
223 Tukey's *post-hoc* test after ANOVA (Table 4). Additionally, we calculated confidence
224 intervals for all the parameters to illustrate the uncertainty in parameter estimation. All
225 dose-response analyses were made on R (R Core Team, 2017). We used drc package for
226 curve selection and nls function for parameter estimation (Ritz et al., 2015). The
227 selected curves had three parameters (Eqn 1) for *O. acuminatum*, *O. ibericum* and *O.*
228 *striatum*, and four parameters for *O. rupestre* (Eqn 2). We performed ANOVA and
229 Tukey's *post-hoc* test to test the effect of PAR exposure time on the spore germination
230 percentage of each species, and to test the interspecific differences in the spore
231 germination percentage for each UV_{BE} dose (Appendix S2).
232

233 RESULTS

234

235 Spore germination results are shown in Table 2. At the beginning of the experiment, *O.*
236 *ibericum* showed the lowest germination percentage, whereas values were higher and
237 similar in the remaining species. Under the PAR regime, the overall effect of the
238 exposure period on the germination percentage was not significant for any species.
239 Although *O. ibericum* showed a non-significant decreasing trend in spore germination
240 under only PAR, this decrease required 12 h of PAR exposure, whereas decreases under
241 the PAR + UV regimes were much more rapid. Indeed, under the PAR + UV regime, *O.*
242 *acuminatum* and *O. ibericum* percentages decreased strongly (down or near to zero)
243 after an intermediate exposure (6 h), with the latter species showing a clear decrease
244 even after the low exposure (3 h). In contrast, *O. striatum* maintained high germination
245 percentages after an intermediate exposure, and values clearly decreased only after 12
246 h-exposure. *Orthotrichum rupestre* showed an intermediate performance, retaining (as
247 in *O. striatum*) an important germination percentage after 6 h-exposure, and still an
248 appreciable percentage after 12 h-exposure.

249 The modelling of our germination results, based on the UV_{BE} doses calculated
250 after Flint and Caldwell (2003), paralleled the previous description (Fig. 2, Tables 3 and
251 4). The germination rates in non-UV-irradiated samples at the beginning of the
252 experiment (Tp parameter) were high in the four species analyzed, with *O. ibericum*
253 showing lower values than *O. acuminatum* and *O. rupestre*. The Bt parameter expressed
254 the minimum germination percentage at the end of the experiment, when the spores had
255 received $44.4 \text{ kJ m}^{-2} UV_{BE}$. There were no significant differences in Bt between the two
256 hygrochastic species and the xerochastic *O. rupestre*, all of which showed low values

257 (zero in *O. ibericum*), whereas values were significantly higher in the xerochastic *O.*
258 *striatum*. The confidence intervals for *Bt* overlapped between *O. acuminatum* and *O.*
259 *ibericum*, while both *O. rupestre* and *O. striatum* had higher and non-overlapping
260 confidence intervals. *IC50* varied between 11.46 kJ m⁻² UV_{BE} in *O. ibericum* and 23.82
261 in *O. striatum*. The hygrochastic species showed similar *IC50* values, that were
262 significantly lower than those of xerochastic species (Table 4). These interspecific
263 differences were mostly corroborated performing ANOVA on the non-modelled data of
264 spore germination (Appendix S2), particularly at moderate UV_{BE} doses. At low and high
265 UV_{BE} doses, the interspecific differences were more subtle due to the slight damage in
266 all species except *O. ibericum*, or to the severe damage in every species, respectively.
267 Results were similar when other action spectra were applied.

268 Ultrastructural observations are shown according to the level of damage
269 observed (Figs. 3-5), and a summary of the observations for each species and UV_{BE}
270 dose applied is shown in Table 5. Non-damaged spores (Fig. 3) corresponded to both
271 control (PAR regime) and uncultured spores, which were considered as equivalent. In
272 the four species studied, we observed three main layers in the cell wall: perine, exine
273 and intine. The perine consisted of small sculpturing elements (except in *O. rupestre*,
274 see Fig. 3 f, g). The exine was very thin (less than 0.2 μm), and the intine consisted of
275 two continuous layers (Fig. 3 a, c, e, g, h). The germination process involved the
276 production of a third, innermost intine layer, discontinuous and irregular, with a loose
277 fibrillar appearance (Fig. 3 e, i). The cytoplasm presented almost no vacuolization. The
278 nucleus was usually centered, with a granular nucleoplasm; sometimes a prominent
279 nucleolus was visible (Fig. 3 h). The chloroplasts were typically fusiform, with densely
280 packed thylakoids. Storage substances included cytoplasmic lipids, and intraplasmic
281 starch and plastoglobuli. Cytoplasmic lipids were usually predominant, appearing as

282 homogeneous droplets (Fig. 3 f-i) or as partially filled, electron-dense globules (Fig. 3 f-
283 h), usually interpreted as the product of some degree of lipid solubilization during the
284 embedding process (Olesen and Mogensen, 1978). Regarding storage substances, there
285 were some interspecific differences: in the two hygrochastic species, *O. acuminatum*
286 and *O. ibericum*, they were present in lesser quantities; and, in plastids, starch was more
287 abundant in *O. rupestre*, whereas plastoglobuli were predominant in the remaining
288 species. Some slight cytoplasmic retraction was often visible (Fig. 3 a, d, e, h).
289 Cytoplasmic vacuolization (Fig. 3 d, i) and lamellar bodies (Fig. 3 e) were only
290 occasional.

291 Moderately damaged spores (Fig. 4) were those conserving their overall cell
292 integrity after UV irradiation. The spore wall stratification was seemingly unaltered
293 (Fig. 4 b, e, g, k). The cytoplasm showed occasionally some retraction (Fig. 4 c, l,
294 double arrows), although similar to that observed in non-UV-irradiated spores (e.g., Fig.
295 3 a, e, double arrows). The nucleus, when observed, showed no apparent changes (e.g.,
296 Fig. 4 a). The chloroplasts still showed mostly a typical appearance (e.g., Fig. 4 a, c, f,
297 m). Nevertheless, signs of damage were frequent. In all four species we observed a
298 more pronounced cytoplasmic vacuolization (e.g., Fig. 4 b, k, l), and the frequent
299 occurrence of lamellar bodies (e.g., Fig. 4 b, l). In the chloroplasts, the thylakoids were
300 often more loosely packed, and some expanded intra-thylakoid spaces were often
301 observable (e.g., Fig. 4 g, n). Occasional alterations in the chloroplast shape were
302 observed (Fig. 4 n). Some changes were seen to affect the storage substances. In *O.*
303 *ibericum* and *O. striatum* (Fig. 4 c, e, j), the cytoplasm presented an electron-dense,
304 fragmented, solid-like substance, probably corresponding to partially dissolved lipid
305 droplets produced during the dehydrating/embedding protocol, but with an altered
306 structure probably due to UV. We also observed a frequent extra-membrane lining

307 consisting of electron-dense vesicles (Fig. 4 a, k, arrowheads) or spine-like structures
308 (Fig. 4 d, l, arrowheads). In both xerochastic species (*O. rupestre* and *O. striatum*),
309 spores with this comparatively well-preserved cell integrity were observed at low and
310 intermediate UV_{BE} doses (occasionally, even at the high dose: Fig. 4 i, o). On the
311 contrary, in the two hygrochastic species (*O. acuminatum* and *O. ibericum*), similarly
312 well-preserved stages were restricted to spores exposed to low UV_{BE} doses (Table 5).

313 Lethally damaged spores (Fig. 5) corresponded to UV-irradiated spores with
314 evident, profound damage in their organelles or cell structure. Although the cell wall
315 showed little alteration, the cytoplasm, in the four species, presented frequently a
316 pronounced retraction, extensive vacuolization and internal disorganization. When
317 visible, the nucleus was distorted and the nucleoplasm showed irregular aggregations
318 (Fig. 5 a). The chloroplasts, when distinguishable (Fig. 5 a, f), were deformed and with
319 altered endomembrane structure. In addition to expanded intra-thylakoidal spaces, the
320 thylakoids themselves were clumped irregularly. In more advanced degeneration stages,
321 their structure was completely disorganized and unobservable (Fig. 5 b, c, d, e). Some
322 changes were observed in the lipid droplets, such as their merging into larger units (Fig.
323 5 d). We observed no lamellar bodies in these spores. This lethal damage was observed,
324 in xerochastic species, only at the high UV_{BE} dose used, and in hygrochastic species at
325 both intermediate and high UV_{BE} doses (Table 5).

326

327 **DISCUSSION**

328

329 Spore viability in four species of the moss genus *Orthotrichum* was negatively
330 influenced by UV_{BE} radiation. The four species showed a reduction in the germination
331 capacity in a UV_{BE} dose-dependent manner (Fig. 2) and, concomitantly, a progressively
332 stronger ultrastructural damage was observed (Figs. 3-5; Table 5). Although the
333 deleterious effects of UV radiation were common to the four species, there were strong
334 interspecific differences in the level of damage. As hypothesized, spores of hygrochastic
335 species (*O. acuminatum* and *O. ibericum*) were much more UV-sensitive than those of
336 xerochastic species (*O. rupestre* and *O. striatum*), revealing that the dispersal strategy of
337 moss spores is related to UV tolerance.

338

339 ***UV radiation and spore germination***—The reduction in spore germination was
340 modelled using logistic curves, confirming that the *IC50* increased in the order *O.*
341 *ibericum* = *O. acuminatum* < *O. rupestre* < *O. striatum* (Tables 3-4). This type of model
342 fitting allows a straightforward comparison of the severity of UV damage across studies
343 and species, because the *IC50* values can be compared even when different doses are
344 applied. Besides, the good fit of the models, and the feasible number of data points
345 required to find an adequate model, provide a useful method towards the generalization
346 of the study of UV resistance in bryophytes.

347 Spore mortality rates were high (78-100%) at the high UV_{BE} dose applied in our
348 study, which was approximately equivalent to 3 d of summer radiation conditions at the
349 collection sites. However, most spores of the four species survived to the low dose
350 applied. In *Physcomitrella patens*, spores also failed to germinate when using

351 comparable UV-B levels to our high dose, whereas one third of that dose hardly
352 influenced spore germination (Wolf et al., 2010). No other comparable data on the
353 effects of UV (either UV-B or UV-A) radiation on bryophyte spores are available in the
354 literature, although many data exist in algae and seed plants. Regarding UV-B, zoospore
355 germination decreased in brown algae under UV-B radiation in most of the studies
356 carried out, although the UV-B doses applied were, in general, considerably lower than
357 those applied in our experiment (Dring et al., 1996; Wiencke et al., 2004; Roleda et al.,
358 2006b; Wiencke et al., 2007; Steinhoff et al., 2008). Thus, although germination results
359 may be difficult to compare between the different studies, due to the use of diverse
360 species and experimental conditions, it seems that brown algae zoospores are more UV-
361 B-sensitive than the moss spores studied here, probably because 1) zoospore cell walls
362 are thin and are synthesized some hours after release (Steinhoff et al., 2008); and 2)
363 most brown algae species studied had an Arctic origin, and hence were naturally
364 exposed to relatively low UV-B levels. Spore germination of a green alga was also
365 particularly susceptible to UV-B (Han et al., 2004). Curiously, UV-B did not influence
366 germination of red algae spores under field or laboratory conditions, but UV-B doses
367 applied were again relatively low (Jiang et al., 2007; Roleda et al., 2008). Regarding
368 pollen of seed plants, germination could be inhibited or non-influenced by a direct
369 exposure to UV-B, depending on both the species used and the UV-B dose applied (Flint
370 and Caldwell, 1984; Santos et al., 1998; Torabinejad et al., 1998; Feng et al., 2000; He
371 et al., 2007; Zhang et al., 2014; Koubouris et al., 2015). Taking into account all these
372 results, it can be concluded that the spores of the moss species studied seemed to be
373 moderately UV tolerant, being closer in this regard to pollen of seed plants than to algal
374 spores. Data from other evolutionary lineages are needed to outline a more complete
375 evolutionary picture of the UV tolerance of spores and pollen.

376 In UV experimentation, results obtained in the laboratory are usually difficult to
377 extrapolate to field conditions, and UV effects on spore germination may be more subtle
378 in the field than in the laboratory (Roleda et al., 2006b). Nevertheless, moderate realistic
379 doses of, particularly, UV-B wavelengths were used in our study, and thus extrapolation
380 to field conditions seems plausible.

381 The effect of UV-A wavelengths on spore germination cannot be reliably
382 assessed from our study, given that the UV-A doses applied were relatively very low in
383 comparison with ambient solar levels. Thus, the specific effect of UV-A radiation on
384 bryophyte spore germination merits further research. UV-A radiation inhibited spore
385 germination in some species of brown algae (Roleda et al., 2006b), but not in other
386 species (Tala et al., 2007; Steinhoff et al., 2008), as occurred in maize pollen (Wang et
387 al., 2010). Overall, the UV-A effect on spore germination in brown and green algae was
388 found to be more slight (if any) than the UV-B effect (Wiencke et al., 2000, 2004; Han
389 et al., 2004; Tala et al., 2007; Steinhoff et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2010), even using UV-
390 A doses much higher than those applied in our study.

391

392 ***UV radiation and spore ultrastructure***—Control spores, as well as mature
393 rehydrated uncultured spores, were as previously described for the genus *Orthotrichum*
394 (Medina and Estébanez, 2014). In spores exposed to increasing doses of UV_{BE} radiation,
395 diverse and progressive ultrastructural damage was found in a species-dependent
396 manner (Figs. 3-5; Table 5). In general, the first ultrastructural signs of UV_{BE} damage
397 were an increase of vacuolization and lamellar bodies, as well as expanded intra-
398 thylakoid spaces in the chloroplasts, a lining of extra-membrane material, and changes
399 in lipid droplets. The most damaged spores showed extensive cytoplasm vacuolization
400 and pronounced retraction, alterations in the nucleus, irregular aggregations in the

401 nucleoplasm, shape changes and thylakoid clumping in the chloroplasts, aggregation of
402 lipid droplets into larger units, and finally, complete disorganization.

403 This is the first time that UV-induced ultrastructural damage is described in
404 bryophyte spores, since previous studies carried out in bryophytes only considered
405 vegetative tissues (Barsig et al., 1998; Haapala et al., 2010; Hui et al., 2013, 2014). In
406 other photosynthetic organisms, only a few studies about the ultrastructural effects of
407 UV radiation on spores or pollen are available. UV-B caused a strong damage to the
408 zoospores of a brown alga, that showed a mottled nucleoplasm, chloroplasts with
409 plastoglobuli, and changes in the mitochondria structure from crista- to sacculus-type
410 (Steinhoff et al., 2008). In pollen, large amounts of electron dense deposits were seen
411 throughout the cytoplasm and in association with the pollen wall in maize (Santos et al.,
412 1998), and alterations in exine ornamentation were found in soybean (Koti et al., 2004).

413

414 *Interspecific differences and UV tolerance mechanisms*—In our study, the
415 effects of UV_{BE} radiation on both germination and ultrastructure of moss spores was
416 species-dependent. This was expected because, in general, responses of photosynthetic
417 organisms to UV are species-specific (Martínez-Abaigar and Núñez-Olivera, 2011;
418 Suchar and Robberecht, 2016), including germination responses of brown algae spores
419 (e.g., Wiencke et al., 2004) and pollen of seed plants (Torabinejad et al., 1998; Feng et
420 al., 2000; Zhang et al., 2014). The mechanisms underlying the species-dependent UV
421 tolerance of bryophyte spores are currently unknown. In zoospores of brown algae, UV
422 tolerance has been related to the accumulation of UV-screening compounds, such as
423 phlorotannins (Wiencke et al., 2007; Gruber et al., 2011) and phloroglucinol (Roleda et
424 al., 2006c). In maize pollen, a similar protecting role has been attributed to unidentified
425 cell wall-bound UV-screening compounds (Santos et al., 1998). This kind of

426 compounds, mainly of phenolic nature, have also been found in bryophyte spores
427 (Rozema et al., 2001), but their role in spore UV tolerance is unknown. Apart from
428 these mechanisms, the ultrastructural observation of a lining of extra-membrane
429 material, probably a result of an excretion process, could represent a UV protection.
430

431 ***Relationship of spore UV tolerance with dispersal strategy, distribution range***
432 ***and ecological preferences***—The spore UV tolerance of the *Orthotrichum* species tested
433 was related to their dispersal strategy, with xerochastic species (*O. rupestre* and *O.*
434 *striatum*) more UV tolerant than hygrochastic species (*O. acuminatum* and *O.*
435 *ibericum*), in terms of both germination capacity and ultrastructural damage. The two
436 xerochastic species also showed some differences in UV tolerance between them, with
437 *O. striatum* more tolerant than *O. rupestre*, given that the former, in comparison with
438 the latter, showed higher *IC50* values, higher spore survival rates and less ultrastructural
439 damage at the high UV_{BE} dose applied.

440 The xerochastic strategy is more frequent than the hygrochastic one in the genus
441 *Orthotrichum* and also, in temperate regions, in mosses in general (Pais, 1967; Mueller
442 and Neumann, 1988). The contrast in UV tolerance between hygrochastic and
443 xerochastic species can indicate the differences in the most likely conditions of spore
444 release and dispersal between both strategies. The period of spore release in
445 hygrochastic and xerochastic species may not be strictly seasonal, but spores of
446 hygrochastic species would preferentially be released in wet-rainy-cloudy days, whereas
447 those of xerochastic species would be so in dry sunny days (Mueller and Neumann,
448 1988). Given that clouds can significantly reduce the UV amount (particularly UV-B)
449 reaching the ground (Németh et al., 1996), the spores of hygrochastic species would be
450 exposed to lower UV doses in the moment of release. In addition, spores dispersed

451 under wet conditions are less likely to be transported over long distances (Lazarenko,
452 1957; Mueller and Neumann, 1988). Thus, spores of xerochastic species are exposed to
453 higher UV levels in nature, which matches well with the higher UV tolerance they
454 showed in our study. This interpretation is also supported by the lower accumulation of
455 spore lipids and the higher proportion of bicellular spores in the hygrochastic species of
456 *Orthotrichum*, which are regarded as typical features of species developing a safe-site
457 strategy, being linked to a more rapid germination and shorter dispersal distances
458 (Medina and Estébanez, 2014).

459 Additionally, the results obtained are congruent with the fact that xerochastic
460 species are more widely geographically distributed than hygrochastic species.
461 Specifically, both *O. striatum* and *O. rupestre* are very widely distributed (the former
462 throughout the Holarctic region and the latter almost cosmopolitan), whereas *O.*
463 *acuminatum*, and especially *O. ibericum*, have more restricted distributions (Lara et al.,
464 2016). Thus, a reduced UV tolerance may substantially decrease the probability that
465 viable spores successfully reach appropriate distant places to develop. Certainly, the
466 expansion potential of a species is the outcome of the interaction between spore
467 resistance and diaspore productivity, including the quantity and quality of the diaspores
468 (Laaka-Lindberg et al., 2000; Laenen et al., 2016). In addition, adult plant
469 characteristics, such as the physiological tolerance of mature plants and their
470 competitive ability, also influence the distribution ranges of the species (e.g., Soberón
471 and Peterson, 2005). However, it is important to note that while all these factors are
472 usually accounted for when studying the species distribution ranges, the role of UV
473 resistance of the dispersing units has been considered only rarely (Van Zanten, 1976,
474 1978; Van Zanten and Gradstein, 1988). In seed plants, UV-B and UV-A radiation

475 influenced pollen viability in species showing long-distance dispersal (Bohrerova et al.,
476 2009).

477

478 **CONCLUSION**

479 We have studied for the first time the effects of UV radiation on the viability of
480 bryophyte spores, using germination capacity and ultrastructure as response variables.
481 Using four species of the moss genus *Orthotrichum* as a case study, we found that
482 increasing UV_{BE} doses caused progressively higher reductions in the spore germination
483 capacity and, concomitantly, stronger ultrastructural damage including cytoplasmic and
484 plastid alterations. We can assume that the damage caused by UV radiation on key cell
485 components is directly related with the observed reduction in germination.

486 Interestingly, UV effects were related to the spore dispersal strategy of the
487 species, and were more negative in hygrochastic than in xerochastic species (spores
488 dispersed under wet or dry conditions, respectively). The higher UV tolerance of
489 xerochastic spores would enable them to be dispersed to longer distances than
490 hygrochastic spores, thus extending more efficiently the distribution range of the
491 corresponding species. Further studies should determine if our findings can be applied
492 to other mosses and photosynthetic organisms in general, confirming or rejecting that
493 spore dispersal is influenced by UV tolerance. Finally, spores of the moss species
494 studied seemed to be more UV tolerant than algal spores, being closer in this regard to
495 pollen of seed plants. More research is needed to fully understand the ecological,
496 chorological and phylogenetic implications of UV tolerance in bryophyte spores.

497

498

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500

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678

679 **DATA ACCESSIBILITY**

680 The data presented in this paper are shown in the main text.

681

682 **TABLE 1.** Doses (kJ m^{-2}) of ultraviolet (UV) radiation applied to the spores in the two regimes imposed: photosynthetically active radiation
 683 alone (PAR), and PAR + UV. Unweighted UV-A and UV-B doses are shown, together with biologically effective UV or UV-B doses (UV_{BE} or
 684 UV-B_{BE} , respectively), calculated on the basis of the action spectra specified, differentiating the exposure periods.

685

Exposure period (h)	PAR					PAR + UV				
	UV-A	UV-B	UV-B _{BE} (Caldwell, 1971)	UV-B _{BE} (Setlow, 1974)	UV _{BE} (Flint and Caldwell, 2003)	UV-A	UV-B	UV-B _{BE} (Caldwell, 1971)	UV-B _{BE} (Setlow, 1974)	UV _{BE} (Flint and Caldwell, 2003)
3	0.08	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	28.1	24.4	12.3	12.0	11.1
6	0.17	0.08	0.04	0.04	0.04	56.2	48.8	24.6	24.0	22.2
12	0.34	0.16	0.08	0.09	0.07	112.3	97.7	49.2	48.0	44.4

686

687

688

689

690 **TABLE 2.** Percentage of germinated spores of the four species used in the two radiation regimes imposed (photosynthetically active radiation
691 alone, PAR, and PAR + UV-B), differentiating the exposure periods. Germination results before radiation exposure (0 h) are also shown. Means $\pm$
692 SE are shown ($n = 3$). These results have been modelled in Fig. 2.

693

Species	0 h	PAR			PAR + UV-B		
		3 h	6 h	12 h	3 h	6 h	12 h
<i>O. acuminatum</i>	94.3 $\pm$ 2.2	92.0 $\pm$ 1.5	91.3 $\pm$ 2.8	93.0 $\pm$ 0.6	90.0 $\pm$ 0.5	0.0 $\pm$ 0	1.3 $\pm$ 0.5
<i>O. ibericum</i>	80.0 $\pm$ 3.1	81.0 $\pm$ 0.6	76.3 $\pm$ 7.5	61.0 $\pm$ 7.5	55.6 $\pm$ 1.2	0.0 $\pm$ 0	0.0 $\pm$ 0
<i>O. rupestre</i>	90.6 $\pm$ 3.8	83.6 $\pm$ 2.4	86.6 $\pm$ 2.3	81.0 $\pm$ 1.7	80.0 $\pm$ 2.6	23.6 $\pm$ 2.3	7.3 $\pm$ 1.3
<i>O. striatum</i>	88.6 $\pm$ 4.2	81.3 $\pm$ 2.4	93.3 $\pm$ 1.4	91.0 $\pm$ 2.6	83.6 $\pm$ 4.7	84.6 $\pm$ 3.6	22.0 $\pm$ 9.0

694

695 **TABLE 3.** Average values and confidence intervals of the modeled parameters in the
696 different *Orthotrichum* species used (see Fig. 2). *Tp* is the maximum germination
697 percentage when no treatment is applied. *Bt* is the minimum asymptotic germination
698 percentage. *IC50* is the biologically effective UV (UV_{BE}) dose, calculated using the
699 action spectrum by Flint and Caldwell (2013), that produces a response halfway
700 between the maximum and the minimum. *Hill* refers to the symmetry of the curve.
701

Parameter	Species	Estimate	Confidence intervals	
			lower (10%)	upper (90%)
Tp	<i>O. acuminatum</i>	94.33	92.69	95.97
	<i>O. ibericum</i>	80.00	77.86	82.14
	<i>O. rupestre</i>	91.14	87.01	95.27
	<i>O. striatum</i>	86.17	80.70	91.63
Bt	<i>O. acuminatum</i>	0.67	0.00	1.83
	<i>O. ibericum</i>	0.00	0.00	1.51
	<i>O. rupestre</i>	7.31	3.53	11.08
	<i>O. striatum</i>	22.00	14.27	29.73
IC50	<i>O. acuminatum</i>	12.41	12.18	12.65
	<i>O. ibericum</i>	11.46	11.39	11.53
	<i>O. rupestre</i>	17.42	16.26	18.58
	<i>O. striatum</i>	23.82	21.04	26.61
Hill	<i>O. rupestre</i>	0.12	0.09	0.14

702
703
704

705 **TABLE 4.** Interspecific differences in the main parameters (*Tp*, *Bt* and
706 *IC50*, see Table 3) of the sigmoidal dose-response curves used to model the
707 effect of the biologically effective UV dose on the spore germination of four
708 *Orthotrichum* species (see Fig. 2). Differences were assessed using Tukey's
709 *post-hoc* test after ANOVA (for *Tp*, $F_{3,31} = 5.72$, $P = 0.003$; for *Bt*, $F_{3,31} =$
710 10.42 , $P = 0.001$; for *IC50*, $F_{3,31} = 26.86$, $P < 0.001$). Mean differences for
711 each parameter between the four species and the corresponding *P* values are
712 shown. NS, non-significant.

Parameter	Species		Mean difference	<i>P</i> -value
Tp	<i>O. acuminatum</i>	<i>O. ibericum</i>	14.33	0.0026
	<i>O. acuminatum</i>	<i>O. rupestre</i>	3.19	0.8341 (NS)
	<i>O. acuminatum</i>	<i>O. striatum</i>	8.17	0.1401 (NS)
	<i>O. ibericum</i>	<i>O. rupestre</i>	-11.14	0.0298
	<i>O. ibericum</i>	<i>O. striatum</i>	-6.17	0.3528 (NS)
	<i>O. rupestre</i>	<i>O. striatum</i>	4.97	0.5624 (NS)
Bt	<i>O. acuminatum</i>	<i>O. ibericum</i>	0.67	0.9988 (NS)
	<i>O. acuminatum</i>	<i>O. rupestre</i>	-6.64	0.4858 (NS)
	<i>O. acuminatum</i>	<i>O. striatum</i>	-21.33	0.0002
	<i>O. ibericum</i>	<i>O. rupestre</i>	-7.31	0.4027 (NS)
	<i>O. ibericum</i>	<i>O. striatum</i>	-22.00	0.0002
	<i>O. rupestre</i>	<i>O. striatum</i>	-14.69	0.0165
IC50	<i>O. acuminatum</i>	<i>O. ibericum</i>	0.95	0.9256 (NS)
	<i>O. acuminatum</i>	<i>O. rupestre</i>	-5.01	0.0182
	<i>O. acuminatum</i>	<i>O. striatum</i>	-11.41	< 0.0001
	<i>O. ibericum</i>	<i>O. rupestre</i>	-5.96	0.0039
	<i>O. ibericum</i>	<i>O. striatum</i>	-12.36	< 0.0001
	<i>O. rupestre</i>	<i>O. striatum</i>	-6.40	0.0019

713

714 **TABLE 5.** Summary of the main ultrastructural alterations observed in each of the four species of *Orthotrichum* used when exposed to the three
 715 different exposure periods. Freq., frequently observed. Occas., occasionally observed.

Species	Exposure period		
	3 h	6 h	12 h
<i>O. acuminatum</i>	<p>Most spores observed: moderately altered</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Slight cytoplasmic retraction and vacuolization - Extra-membrane lining of vesicles (freq.) - Lamellar bodies (freq.) - Alterations in the lipidic substances (occas.) - Chloroplasts altered: shape, internal structure (occas.) <p>Also observed: spores with no alterations (occas.)</p>	<p>All spores observed: profoundly altered</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pronounced cytoplasmic retraction and vacuolization - No lamellar bodies - Scarce lipidic substances - Chloroplasts profoundly altered: shape, internal structure 	<p>All spores observed: dead</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Very pronounced cytoplasmic retraction - Complete cytoplasmic disorganization
<i>O. ibericum</i>	<p>All spores observed: profoundly altered</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pronounced cytoplasmic retraction, some vacuolization - Extra-membrane lining of vesicles (freq.) - Lamellar bodies (occas.) - Alterations in the lipidic substances (freq.) - Chloroplasts altered: shape, internal structure (freq.) 	<p>All spores observed: dead</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Very pronounced cytoplasmic retraction - Complete cytoplasmic disorganization 	<p>All spores observed: dead</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Very pronounced cytoplasmic retraction - Complete cytoplasmic disorganization
<i>O. rupestre</i>	<p>Most spores observed: moderately altered</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cytoplasmic retraction and vacuolization (occas.) - Extra-membrane lining of vesicles (occas.) - Lamellar bodies (occas.) - Chloroplasts slightly altered: storage substances (freq.) <p>Also observed: spores with alterations in chloroplast shape and internal structure (freq.)</p>	<p>All spores observed: moderately altered</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cytoplasmic retraction and vacuolization (freq.) - Extra-membrane lining of vesicles (occas.) - Lamellar bodies (occas.) - Chloroplasts slightly altered: storage substances and internal structure (freq.) <p>Also observed: 1) dead spores with complete cytoplasmic disorganization (freq.), and 2) spores almost unaltered (occas.)</p>	<p>Most spores observed: dead</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Very pronounced cytoplasmic retraction - Complete cytoplasmic disorganization <p>Also observed: occasional spores almost unaltered</p>
<i>O. striatum</i>	<p>Most spores observed: moderately altered</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cytoplasmic retraction and vacuolization (occas.) - Extra-membrane lining of vesicles (occas.) - Lamellar bodies (freq.) - Alterations in the lipidic substances (occas.) - Chloroplasts with less starch (freq.) 	<p>Most spores observed: profoundly altered</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cytoplasmic retraction and vacuolization (freq.) - Extra-membrane lining of vesicles (freq.) - Lamellar bodies (occas.) - Alterations in the lipidic substances (freq.) - Chloroplasts altered: shaper, internal structure (freq.) <p>Also observed: spores with no alterations (freq.)</p>	<p>Most spores observed: profoundly altered</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pronounced cytoplasmic retraction and vacuolization (freq.) - Extra-membrane lining of vesicles (occas.) - Lamellar bodies (occas.) - Alterations in the lipidic substances (freq.) - Chloroplasts altered: shape, internal structure (freq.) <p>Also observed: spores almost unaltered (occas.)</p>

716

717 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

718

719 **FIGURE 1.** Spectral irradiances supplied to the spores in the two regimes imposed:
720 photosynthetically active radiation alone (PAR, solid line), and PAR + UV (dashed
721 line). Both curves are coincident for wavelengths higher than 395 nm.

722

723 **FIGURE 2.** Percentage of germinated spores of four *Orthotrichum* species in response
724 to the biologically effective UV radiation (UV_{BE}) doses applied in the PAR
725 (photosynthetically active radiation) + UV regime. UV_{BE} doses were calculated using
726 the action spectrum of Flint and Caldwell (2003). Data for 0 UV_{BE} dose correspond to
727 germination before radiation exposure. Data were modelled using dose-response
728 sigmoid curves. Means $\pm$ SE are shown ($n = 3$).

729

730 **FIGURE 3.** TEM micrographs of non-damaged spores of the four *Orthotrichum* species
731 used. *Orthotrichum acuminatum*: (a) spore wall stratification, cytoplasm with some
732 occasional retraction (double arrow), almost no vacuolization, and large, fusiform
733 plastids with densely packed thylakoids; (b) spore with scarce storage substances,
734 including undissolved and partially dissolved lipid droplets, and an internal cell
735 tabication (white angle); (c) detail of the spore wall stratification. *Orthotrichum*
736 *ibericum*: (d) spore showing a third, discontinuous intine layer (I3), and cytoplasm with
737 some localized vacuolization and low quantities of storage substances; (e) cell wall
738 stratification with loose, fibrillar structure in the innermost intine layer; cytoplasm
739 retraction (double arrow), a plastid containing scarce plastoglobuli, and a lamellar body
740 (white angle). *Orthotrichum rupestre*: (f) spore with abundant storage substances: lipid

741 droplets (both undissolved and partially dissolved), and intraplastidial starch; (g) spore
742 detail with different kinds of storage substances. *Orthotrichum striatum*: (h) spore with
743 abundant lipid droplets, fusiform plastids and a central nucleus; (i) detail of the
744 innermost discontinuous intine layer, some cytoplasmic retraction and vacuolization,
745 undissolved lipid droplets and plastids with some plastoglobuli. Chl, chloroplasts; dL,
746 partially dissolved lipid droplets; E, exine; I, intine; I1, I2 and I3, intine layers; m,
747 mitochondria; N, nucleus; Pe, perine; pg, plastoglobuli; s, starch; SW, spore wall; uL,
748 undissolved lipid droplets; v, vacuoles. Scale bars = 2 μm .

749

750 **FIGURE 4.** TEM micrographs of moderately damaged spores of the four *Orthotrichum*
751 species used. *Orthotrichum acuminatum* irradiated with low UV_{BE}: (a) frequent
752 lamellar bodies (white angles), chloroplasts with expanded intra-thylakoidal spaces
753 (asterisks), and extra-membrane lining of electron-dense, small vesicles (arrowheads);
754 (b) cytoplasmic vacuolization (v) and lamellar bodies (white angles). *Orthotrichum*
755 *ibericum* irradiated with low UV_{BE}: (c) cytoplasmic retraction (double arrow) and
756 altered lipid droplets (aL); (d) extra-membrane lining of spine-like structures
757 (arrowheads); (e) detail of the altered lipid droplets. *Orthotrichum rupestre* irradiated
758 with low UV_{BE}: (f) spore with well-preserved plastids and both normal and altered lipid
759 droplets; (g) spore showing both normal and altered lipid droplets and chloroplasts with
760 large intra-thylakoidal spaces (asterisks). *Orthotrichum rupestre* irradiated with
761 intermediate UV_{BE}: (h) spore showing well-preserved chloroplasts and some
762 cytoplasmic vacuolization. *Orthotrichum rupestre* irradiated with high UV_{BE}: (i)
763 spore with well-preserved cell integrity despite extensive vacuolization. *Orthotrichum*
764 *striatum* irradiated with low UV_{BE}: (j) spore with altered lipid droplets; (k)
765 cytoplasmic vacuolization, one lamellar body (white angle), and an extra-membrane

766 lining of small, electron-dense vesicles (arrowheads). *Orthotrichum striatum*
767 **irradiated with intermediate UV_{BE}:** (l) cytoplasmic retraction (double arrow), lamellar
768 bodies (white angles), and extra-membranal spine-like structures (arrowheads); (m)
769 cytoplasm filled with altered lipid droplets; (n) altered plastids with expanded intra-
770 thylakoidal spaces (asterisks), cytoplasmic vacuolization and lamellar bodies (white
771 angle). *Orthotrichum striatum irradiated with high UV_{BE}:* (o) well-preserved cell
772 integrity despite of altered lipid droplets and expanded intra-thylakoidal spaces in
773 plastids (asterisks). aL, altered lipid droplets; Chl, chloroplasts; dL, partially dissolved
774 lipid droplets; E, exine; I, intine; I1, I2 and I3, intine layers; m, mitochondria; N,
775 nucleus; Pe, perine; pg, plastoglobuli; s, starch; SW, spore wall; uL, undissolved lipid
776 droplets; v, vacuoles. Scale bars = 2 μ m.

777

778 **FIGURE 5.** TEM micrographs of lethally damaged spores of the four *Orthotrichum*
779 species used. *Orthotrichum acuminatum irradiated with intermediate UV_{BE}:* (a)
780 distorted nucleus and irregularly aggregated nucleoplasm, cytoplasm with several
781 vacuoles, and chloroplasts with disorganized internal structure, clumped thylakoids and
782 expanded intra-thylakoid spaces (asterisks). *Orthotrichum acuminatum irradiated*
783 **with high UV_{BE}:** (b) pronounced cytoplasmic retraction (double arrow), extensive
784 vacuolization, and disorganized internal organelles. *Orthotrichum ibericum irradiated*
785 **with intermediate UV_{BE}:** (c) cytoplasm greatly retracted (double arrow) and
786 disorganized. *Orthotrichum rupestre irradiated with intermediate UV_{BE}:* (d)
787 cytoplasm retraction (double arrow), extensive vacuolization, chloroplast
788 disorganization and undissolved lipid droplets merging into large units. *Orthotrichum*
789 *rupestre irradiated with high UV_{BE}:* (e) cytoplasm showing great retraction (double
790 arrow) and internal disorganization. *Orthotrichum striatum irradiated with high*

791 **UV_{BE}**: (f) pronounced cytoplasmic retraction (double arrow), extensive vacuolization,
792 and chloroplasts with expanded intra-thylakoid spaces (asterisks). auL, altered,
793 undissolved lipid droplets; Chl, chloroplasts; N, nucleus; SW, spore wall; v, vacuoles.
794 Scale bars = 2 μm .

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Appendix S1. Description of the model selection procedure for the species used: a) detailed description of the procedure; b) dose-response curves for each species used; and c) Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) for the two dose-response models tested.

Appendix S1a. Detailed description of the model selection procedure.

We used Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) to select the most appropriate model between logistic curves with 3 (Eqn 1) and 4 parameters (Eqn 2).

$$(Eqn1) \ g = B_t + \frac{Tp - B_t}{1 + 10^{(d-IC50)}}$$

$$(Eqn2) \ g = B_t + \frac{Tp - B_t}{1 + 10^{(d-IC50)*Hill}}$$

The Akaike Information Criterion estimates the amount of information lost when a given model is used to represent the data in relation of the number of parameters used. The lower the AIC, the more parsimonious the model is. Additionally, to illustrate the extent of the difference between the two candidate models, we computed the relative likelihood $\exp((AIC_{model1} - AIC_{model2})/2)$, which indicates how many times model 1 is as probable as model 2; in case that model 2 had a perfect fit, the relative likelihood would have a value of 0.

The procedure aimed to find the simplest plausible model, so that we kept the 3-parameter model unless fitting a 4-parameter model provided a significant improvement of the fit. Figure S1 illustrates the fit curves for the four species analyzed and Table S1 shows the AIC values of the two models.

For *O. acuminatum*, the model with 4 parameters did not converge, which indicates that it was not possible to find adequate parameters that represented the data, and thus we kept the 3-parameter curve (eqn1).

For *O. ibericum*, changing the model did not change at all the shape of the curve (note that in Fig. S1b both curves are almost completely overlapped), which implies that the parameter values are robust and will not change regardless of the model used.

For the other two species, there were changes in shape linked to the models. In these two cases we analyzed more in depth the changes in AIC.

In the case of *O. rupestre*, the relative likelihood was 0.2%, indicating that the selected model was far better than the other.

However, in the case of *O. striatum*, the difference in AIC between the two models was low and the relative likelihood was 37.3%. This implies that both models are likely. However, if the more complex model was selected, the differences in IC50 between this species and the rest would have been even larger, so we decided to keep the simpler and more conservative model.

Appendix S1b. Dose–response curves of UV_{BE} on germination rates of the four species analysed: a) *Orthotrichum acuminatum*, b) *O. ibericum*, c) *O. rupestre*, d) *O. striatum*.

Blue and red lines show fit 3- or 4-parameter sigmoidal curves, respectively. Equations are described in this Appendix (Appendix S1a) and Materials and Methods.

Appendix S1c. Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) values for the two dose-response models tested (3- and 4-parameter models). Note that for *O. acuminatum* the 4-parameter model did not converge and thus no AIC value was calculated.

Species	AIC	AIC
	3-parameter model	4-parameter model
<i>O. acuminatum</i>	55.89	-
<i>O. ibericum</i>	62.27	64.27
<i>O. rupestre</i>	88.47	76.14
<i>O. striatum</i>	93.09	95.06

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Appendix S2. Interspecific differences in the spore germination percentage (means $\pm$ SE, $n = 3$) of the four *Orthotrichum* species used in the present study, for each dose of biologically effective UV (UV_{BE}) radiation: 0, low, moderate and high, corresponding to 0, 11.1, 22.2 and 44.4 kJ m⁻² using the action spectrum by Flint and Caldwell (2003). For each dose, different letters mean significant differences between species (F and P values of ANOVA are shown).

UV _{BE} dose	Species				$F_{3,8}$	P -value
	<i>O. acuminatum</i>	<i>O. ibericum</i>	<i>O. rupestre</i>	<i>O. striatum</i>		
0	94.3 $\pm$ 2.2 a	80.0 $\pm$ 3.1 a	90.6 $\pm$ 3.8 a	88.6 $\pm$ 4.2 a	3.2	0.084
Low	90.0 $\pm$ 0.5 b	55.6 $\pm$ 1.2 a	80.0 $\pm$ 2.6 b	83.6 $\pm$ 4.7 b	29.2	0.000
Moderate	0.0 $\pm$ 0 a	0.0 $\pm$ 0 a	23.6 $\pm$ 2.3 b	84.6 $\pm$ 3.6 c	338.4	0.000
High	1.3 $\pm$ 0.5 ab	0.0 $\pm$ 0 a	7.3 $\pm$ 1.3 ab	22.0 $\pm$ 9.0 b	4.8	0.033